

THE ANALYSIS OF ENRICHMENT PROCESS OF TUBEGATAN MINE LOW-GRADE POTASH ORES

Baxrullayeva M.O.

Yangiyer branch of Tashkent Institute of Chemical Technology

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Abstract. *The purpose of the study: comprehensive processing of low-grade sylvinites from Tubegatan mine based on the analysis of the isotherms of the three-component system KCl-NaCl-H₂O at temperatures of 25 °C and 100°C and development of practical studies of a principle scheme.*

The three-component system isotherms of KCl-NaCl- H₂O at temperatures of 25 °C and 100°C were theoretically analyzed, and the water solubility of low-grade sylvinite ores from Tubegatan deposit was studied depending on particle size, temperature, Q:S ratio, and time. Comprehensive processing of low-grade sylvinites from Tubegatan mine based on theoretical analysis and practical research A principle scheme was proposed.

Keywords: *low-grade sylvinite, fraction, potassium chloride, sodium chloride, insoluble part, solubility, theoretical analysis, principle scheme.*

Introduction. The increase in world's population and the reduction of arable land lead to an increase in the demand for mineral fertilizers, which is one of the leading factors in the increase in the price of this product.

The global market of mineral fertilizers includes 3 main segments of nitrogen, phosphorus and potash fertilizers. The share of nitrogen fertilizers in the world market is 56 percent, phosphorus - 24 percent, and potassium - 20 percent.

One of the largest factories producing mineral fertilizers in Uzbekistan is Dehqonabad potash plant, where potassium chloride is produced by the photic method.

Today, special attention is being paid to attracting low-grade potash minerals to the processing industry and creating processing technologies. Therefore, improving the technology of obtaining potassium chloride from low-grade sylvinites is considered one of the urgent tasks.

In this regard, special attention is paid to the development of the scheme to study the mineralogical composition of the low-grade potassium ores of Tubegatan mine in our republic; theoretical analysis of the galurgy method of enrichment and conducting research in laboratory conditions; researching the effect of various technological parameters on product output and finding optimal conditions; complex processing of low-grade sylvinite from Tubegatan mine based on practical research.

Research object and methodology. Low-grade sylvinites from Tubegatan mine were taken as the object of research, and methods of determining their chemical and mineralogical composition were used to determine their solubility in various solvents.

Results and their discussion. The composition of sylvinite mined from Tubegatan mine varies widely, five samples were selected to fully cover the composition of sylvinite, average weight in %: KCl - 9.2, 13.2, 18.3, 26.1, 31.1; NaCl - 54.85, 60.4, 68.9, 66.6, 66.0; water-insoluble residue, etc. - 35.95, 26.2, 12.8, 7.2, 3.13.

A theoretical analysis of the galurgic beneficiation of potash ores of Tubegatan mine was performed. In order to carry out a graphic analysis in the ternary system, considering the sum of

KCl and NaCl as 100%, without taking into account the insoluble part, the composition of the initial raw materials A_n ($A_1, A_2 \dots A_5$) KCl-NaCl-H₂O diagram to the binary solid salt coordinate KCl -NaCl figurative dots inserted.

The melting process was carried out in three variants:

- in the first option, samples were dissolved in clean water, point A;
- in the second option, it was dissolved in a solution containing N^{25} (mixture of water and M^{25} containing solution (1:1) ratio);
- in the third option, it was dissolved in a solution containing M^{25} .

Variants were carried out in two different melting methods:

- full melting method;
- partial melting method.

The ratio of solvent and sylvinitic samples in complete melting and the composition of the solution were found by shouldering the melting light to the points of intersection of melting curves $E_{25} - a^{25}$ and $E_{100} - a^{100}$ at 25°C and 100°C. The composition of the resulting solution is n_n^t ($n_1^{25}, n_2^{25}, n_3^{25}, n_4^{25}, n_5^{25}$ and $n_1^{100}, n_2^{100}, n_3^{100}, n_4^{100}, n_5^{100}$) points.

After removing the insoluble part from the resulting system, the solution m_n^t when evaporated to the point, both at 25°C and at 100°C, only NaCl crystallization m_n^{25} ($m_1^{25}, m_2^{25}, m_3^{25}, m_4^{25}, m_5^{25}$), m_n^{100} ($m_1^{100}, m_2^{100}, m_3^{100}, m_4^{100}, m_5^{100}$) are visible. After separating the NaCl crystals from the suspension formed by evaporation at 100°C, only KCl crystals fall when the E_{100} solution is cooled to 25°C. After separating the potassium chloride crystals, a solution with M^{25} content is formed. The resulting M^{25} solution can be mixed with water in a 1:1 ratio, in the second option, the N^{25} or M^{25} solution can be directly dissolved in it, and the processes in the third option can be carried out.

The first variant of graphic calculations was carried out on the basis of Fig.1. The calculation results are given in Table 1.

Figure 1. Diagram of graphical calculations based on the KCl-NaCl-H₂O system according to the first option

It can be seen from Table 1 that in the method of complete dissolution of the first option (at 25°C), with an increase in KCl in the content of sylvinitic from 9.2% to 31.1%, the amount of water consumed per ton of sylvinitic to obtain a saturated solution from 2.66 t to 1 decreases to .94 t, and at a temperature of 100°C, water consumption for samples decreases from 2.37 to 1.91t.

When melting is carried out at 100°C, water consumption for complete melting of samples is required 0.03 - 0.29t less than the amount required for melting samples at 25°C. The obtained solutions are cleaned from the insoluble parts at 25 °C and 100°C and isothermally evaporated. As a result of evaporation, NaCl initially crystallizes in both isotherms.

Table 1

KCl-NaCl-H₂O diagram, the results of calculating the amount of solvent (water) and the amount of separated NaCl and KCl required in the complex processing of sylvinitic ores by the method of complete dissolution Option №1

Sample serial number	KCl in sylvinitic samples amount, %	the amount of water in sylvinitic to dissolve samples, t	Amount of evaporated water, t	NaCl quantity, t	The amount of KCl, t	
		Calculation equations				
		$\frac{m_{\text{water}}}{A_n n_n} / \frac{m_{\text{salt}}}{A_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} n_n} =$	1) $\frac{m_{\text{vapor}}}{A_n m_n} / \frac{m_{\text{solution}}}{A_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} m_n} =$ 2) $\frac{m_{\text{vapor}}}{(m_{\text{initial solution}} - m_{\text{vapor}})}$	1) $\frac{m_{\text{NaCl}}}{m E_t} = \frac{E_t}{m_n / B m_n}$ 2) $m_{\text{(remaining solution2)}} = m_{\text{(remaining solution1)}} - m_{\text{NaCl}}$	$\frac{m_{\text{KCl}}}{M m} = \frac{E_{100}}{M / C E_{100}}$	
Complete dissolution method , 25 ° C						
1	9,2	2.66	2.19	0.73	-	
2	13.2	2.52	1.79	0.60	-	
3	18.3	2.32	0.95	0.57	-	
4	26.1	2.1	0.76	0.25	-	
5	31.1	1.94	0.34	0.12	-	
Full melting method , 100 ° C						
1	9,2	2.37	2.21	0.86	0.059	
2	13.2	2.25	2.05	0.78	0.089	
3	18.3	2.17	1.87	0.73	0.115	
4	26.1	2.0	1.56	0.66	0.181	
5	31.1	1.91	1.37	0.53	0.203	

As can be seen from Table 1, with an increase in the content of KCl in the ore, the amount of water evaporated at 25 ° C decreases from 2.19 t to 0.34 t, and at 100 ° C - from 2.21 t to 1.37 t.

Based on the theoretical analysis, practical studies were conducted. Water solubility of low-grade sylvinitic ores from Tubegatan deposit was studied as a function of particle size, temperature, Q:S ratio, and time. To study the effect of particle size on the kinetics of melting of low-grade sylvinitic ores from the Tubegatan deposit, the particle size is -10+7 mm; -7+5mm; -5+3mm; -3+1mm; -1+0.5mm; sylvinitic samples (Sample 1 (9.2% KCl) and Sample 2 (18.3% KCl)) were selected. Dissolution of the samples in water was carried out at a Q:S ratio of 1:4 and a temperature of 25°C and 80°C. The dissolution kinetics of the samples was studied. The melting time was 2, 5, 10, 20, 30 minutes. A nomogram was proposed to ensure that it was convenient to

determine the intermediate solubility of technological parameters during technological calculations (Fig. 2).

According to the obtained results, as the temperature increased to 80°C, as a result of the decrease in the size of the particles and the increase in the melting time, the solubility of the samples increased accordingly. At 25°C, the maximum solubility of sample 1 was 70.1%, when the temperature was increased to 80°C, this indicator increased to 88.5%, i.e. 1.26 times. The same situation was repeated in the 2nd sample, when the particle size was $-1+0.5$ mm and the melting time was 30 minutes, the solubility was 95.1%, which is 1.33 times larger compared to the solubility of the same fraction size and time at 25°C (Fig. 2).

a) $t=25^{\circ}\text{C}$ b) $t=80^{\circ}\text{C}$

Figure 2. The dependence of the kinetics of dissolution of low-grade sylvinites on the particle size: sample 1 (9.2% KCl), sample 2 (18.3% KCl)

Experiments on the effect of Q:S ratio, melting time, and temperature on the dissolution of low-grade sylvinites in water. The Q:S ratio is from 1:2 to 1:6, the temperature is from 60°C to 100°C, and the melting time is from 15 to 60 minutes.

Complex processing of low-grade sylvinites based on theoretical analysis and practical research of a principle scheme was proposed (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Principle scheme of complex processing of low-grade sylvinites

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